

WHEN PHONES BECOME TEACHERS: PARENTS' EXPERIENCES OF RELYING ON SMARTPHONES TO SUPPORT HOMEWORK IN RESOURCE-LIMITED SCHOOLS

¹Salman Khan, ²Umar Daraz, ^{*3}Mohammad Hussain

¹MPhil Scholar, Department of Sociology, University of Malakand, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Sociology, University of Malakand, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

^{*3}Lecturer, Department of Sociology University of Malakand, District Dir Lower Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

[*3mohammadhussain.soc@uom.edu.pk](mailto:mohammadhussain.soc@uom.edu.pk)

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Corresponding Author: *

Mohammad Hussain

Abstract

In Pakistan, particularly in resource-limited areas, parents often face challenges in supporting their children's homework due to shortages of textbooks, limited access to qualified teachers, and minimal instructional materials. In Chakdara, District Dir Lower, smartphones have emerged as informal educational tools, enabling parents to bridge these gaps. This study aimed to explore how parents use smartphones to support homework, the challenges and opportunities they encounter, and the impacts of such support on children's learning. A qualitative research design was employed, with 25-30 parents of school-going children from grades 1-10 participating in semi-structured interviews. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's approach, and coding was guided by participants' responses. Findings revealed that smartphones function as essential learning resources, online guides, and tools for co-learning, allowing parents to actively engage in their children's education. Challenges identified included limited digital literacy, connectivity issues, and the risk of children's over-reliance on devices, while opportunities included improved parental knowledge, enhanced engagement, and strengthened parent-child relationships. The study concludes that smartphone-assisted homework support can transform household learning dynamics in resource-limited settings. Recommendations include parental training in digital literacy, structured guidance to balance device use, improved access to connectivity, and school-facilitated digital resources to maximize educational benefits.

1. Introduction

In Pakistan, the rapid spread of mobile technology has reshaped many aspects of daily life, including how education is accessed and supported (Jabeen et al., 2025; Jamil, 2021). Despite government efforts to expand educational infrastructure, significant disparities persist between urban and rural areas. Many schools in resource-limited settings struggle with inadequate facilities, teacher shortages, and limited access to textbooks and digital learning tools. For families living in economically challenged contexts, smartphones have increasingly become a substitute classroom resource, especially for supporting children's homework and learning outside school hours (Daraz, 2024; Khan, 2024).

In Chakdara, Dir Lower, these educational challenges are particularly acute. Schools often operate with minimal teaching aids and overcrowded classrooms, while many parents themselves have limited formal education. Amid these constraints, mobile phones particularly smartphones with internet connectivity have emerged as an unexpected educational lifeline. Parents frequently use WhatsApp, YouTube, and educational apps to help children understand lessons and complete homework. While this trend reflects a degree of resourcefulness, it also raises critical questions about equity, parental burden, and the quality of learning support being provided at home in the absence of structured academic guidance.

The motivation for this study originates from the researcher's own lived experience in Chakdara. Growing up in a community where formal educational support was scarce, I watched parents struggle to help their children with homework. Many expressed frustration as they attempted to interpret textbooks they never fully mastered themselves. A turning point came when I observed a friend whose family could not afford tutors rely almost exclusively on his smartphone to guide his children's homework. This blend of parental concern, limited school resources, and increasing reliance on technology sparked an enduring curiosity: what do parents truly experience when they serve as de-facto teachers through smartphones? Their stories revealed not only the hopes tied to mobile learning but also deep anxieties about academic expectations, technological literacy, and the unseen labor parents invest in their children's education.

This study makes a unique contribution by centering parents' voices in discussions about mobile learning in low-resource educational environments. While much research on educational technology focuses on students or formal schooling systems, few studies examine

how parents negotiate the dual roles of caregiver and educator especially in contexts where smartphones are not supplemental tools but principal means of academic support.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

1. To explore how parents in resource-limited schools in Chakdara, Dir Lower use smartphones to support their children's homework.
2. To examine the challenges and opportunities parents encounter while relying on mobile technology for educational support.
3. To understand the impacts of smartphone-based parental support on children's learning experiences and academic outcomes.

1.2. Research Questions

1. In what ways do parents rely on smartphones to assist their children with homework in resource-limited school contexts?
2. What challenges do parents face when using mobile technology for educational support at home?
3. How do parents perceive the effects of smartphone-based homework support on their children's academic progress?

2. Literature Review

Research on mobile technology and education has expanded rapidly over the past decade, particularly in relation to how smartphones reshape learning beyond formal classrooms (Pedro et al., 2018). Globally, the concept of mobile learning (m-learning) emphasizes the flexibility of portable devices to provide access to information anytime and anywhere, which is especially significant in contexts where schools lack sufficient instructional resources (Abduljawad & Ahmad, 2023; Sarrab et al., 2012). Empirical studies from diverse regions show that smartphones can enhance students' access to explanations, videos, and interactive content, thereby supporting homework completion and independent learning (Anshari et al., 2017; Pimmer et al., 2016). At the same time, the literature cautions that the educational value of smartphones depends heavily on how they are used (Al-Barashdi et al., 2015; Daraz, Hussain, Khan, et al., 2024). Structured and goal-oriented use such as searching for academic content or using learning applications has been associated with improved engagement and understanding, whereas unregulated use, multitasking, and social media distractions are often linked to reduced concentration and weaker academic outcomes (Rajput, 2025; Roberts, 2020).

Within this global discussion, parental involvement emerges as a crucial factor. Educational research consistently shows that when parents engage in their children's homework by monitoring tasks, offering explanations, or encouraging persistence students demonstrate better motivation and achievement (Gonida & Cortina, 2014; Silinskas & Kikas, 2019). With the growth of digital technologies, this involvement increasingly takes place through screens. Studies on parental mediation of digital media highlight that parents who actively guide, discuss, and co-use digital tools with their children can support positive learning behaviours (Goodall et al., 2025; Smahelova et al., 2017). However, these studies also underline challenges: many parents experience limited digital literacy, uncertainty about appropriate educational resources, and tensions between supervising learning and managing children's screen time. Thus, international literature presents smartphones as both enabling tools and sources of strain within family learning dynamics, particularly in settings where formal academic support systems are weak.

In Pakistan, the expansion of smartphone access has similarly influenced educational practices, though research has focused more on students than on parents (Raza et al., 2018). Studies examining Pakistani learners often explore how smartphone use relates to academic performance, noting that educational uses of mobile internet and applications can support learning, while excessive entertainment use may hinder it (Daraz, Khan, et al., 2024; Iqbal & Bhatti, 2020; Jabeen et al., 2025). Parallel research on parental involvement in Pakistan indicates that parents' engagement with schooling such as supervising homework and maintaining communication with teachers positively influences children's academic outcomes (Ahmed, 2023; Daraz, Hussain, & Mulk, 2024; Farooq & Asim, 2020). Nevertheless, many parents face constraints linked to their own educational backgrounds, economic pressures, and limited familiarity with digital technologies. Broader discussions in the Pakistani context also raise concerns about children's screen exposure, behavioural changes, and family interaction patterns, suggesting that technology reshapes not only learning processes but also home environments (Ali et al., 2025; Daraz, Bojnec, & Khan, 2025; Qayyum et al., 2025).

Despite these strands of research, a specific dimension remains underexplored: how parents themselves use smartphones as primary tools to assist with homework when schools lack adequate instructional resources. Much of the national literature addresses either student performance or general patterns of phone usage, rather than the lived experiences of parents

who assume quasi-teacher roles at home through digital means. This gap is particularly relevant in rural and semi-rural areas, where private tutoring and academic support services may be less accessible, and where smartphones may function as substitutes for unavailable educational infrastructure.

In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and especially in areas such as Chakdara in District Dir Lower, educational challenges linked to resource shortages, overcrowded classrooms, and limited teaching materials are widely recognized. However, systematic academic research documenting how families in these communities integrate smartphones into daily homework practices is scarce. The absence of localized empirical evidence means that the realities of parents' digital support practices, their struggles with content comprehension, connectivity issues, or app selection, and the emotional labour involved in guiding children's studies remain largely invisible in scholarly discourse.

The review therefore reveals a clear gap. Global studies acknowledge the dual potential and risks of smartphones in learning and recognize the importance of parental involvement, yet they rarely focus on parents in low-resource schooling contexts acting as *de facto* educators through mobile devices. Pakistani research addresses technology and education, but tends to prioritize students or general parental engagement rather than the specific, technology-mediated homework support practices of parents. At the provincial and district levels, particularly in Chakdara, empirical documentation is minimal. This study responds to that gap by centering parents' experiences in a resource-limited rural setting, examining how they use smartphones to support homework, the challenges and opportunities they encounter, and the strategies they develop to navigate educational constraints.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Paradigm and Design

This study adopted a qualitative research design to investigate parents' lived experiences of using smartphones to support their children's homework in resource-limited school settings (Ahmad et al., 2026). A qualitative approach was considered most suitable because the purpose of the study is to explore meanings, practices, challenges, and perceptions associated with this phenomenon, rather than to quantify variables or test statistical relationships. The research is situated within an interpretivist paradigm, which views reality as socially constructed and

emphasizes understanding participants' subjective interpretations of their experiences within their specific sociocultural context.

Within this qualitative framework, a phenomenological approach was employed to gain deeper insight into how parents experience and make sense of their role in supporting homework through smartphones (Hussain et al., 2025). Phenomenology is particularly relevant to this study as it focuses on individuals' everyday lived experiences and the meanings they attach to them. In this context, it enables an exploration of how parents perceive, interpret, and navigate their evolving role as informal "home teachers" using digital tools in the absence of adequate school resources.

3.2. Study Universe

The study was conducted in Chakdara, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, which was purposively selected as the research setting due to its relevance to the focus of the study. Chakdara represents a semi-rural context where many public and low-fee private schools operate with limited educational resources, including shortages of teaching materials and constrained instructional support. In addition, formal academic assistance such as private tutoring centers is not widely accessible to all families, increasing the burden on parents to support children's learning at home. Despite economic limitations, smartphone use has become common in many households, creating a situation where digital devices serve as alternative sources of information and learning support. The researcher's familiarity with the local sociocultural environment further facilitated access to participants and helped build trust, which is essential for collecting in-depth qualitative data.

3.3. Participants and Sampling

The study focused on parents or primary caregivers of school-going children (Grades 1-10) who had access to at least one smartphone at home, regularly assisted their children with homework, and had children enrolled in resource-limited schools. These criteria ensured that participants had direct and relevant experience with the phenomenon under investigation using smartphones as a tool to support homework in contexts where formal academic resources are limited. A purposive sampling strategy was employed to select information-rich participants who could provide in-depth insights into these experiences. To capture a range of perspectives, variation was sought in terms of mothers and fathers, parents' educational backgrounds, socioeconomic conditions, and the grade levels of their children. In total, approximately 25-30

parents participated in the study, with the final number determined by the point of data saturation, when no substantially new themes or insights emerged from additional interviews (Guest et al., 2006).

3.4. Data Collection Procedures

Data was collected using in-depth semi-structured interviews, which allowed participants to describe their experiences and perspectives in detail while giving the researcher flexibility to probe emerging issues. An interview guide was developed based on the study objectives, focusing on key areas such as how parents use smartphones to support their children's homework, the types of applications, websites, or digital platforms they rely on, the challenges they encounter whether technical, academic, or emotional the perceived impact of smartphone-assisted support on their children's learning, and the strategies they employ to overcome difficulties.

Interviews were conducted in participants' preferred language, either Pashto or Urdu, to ensure comfort and clarity of expression. Each interview lasted approximately 40-60 minutes, and with participants' consent, all sessions were audio-recorded to maintain accuracy and allow for detailed transcription and analysis. The flexible, conversational nature of the semi-structured interviews enabled participants to share rich, personal accounts of their experiences, while the use of a structured guide ensured that all relevant topics related to the research objectives were systematically addressed.

To ensure the trustworthiness and rigor of the study, several strategies were employed. Credibility was maintained through prolonged engagement with participants in the field and by conducting member checks, allowing participants to review summaries of their responses to verify accuracy. Transferability was addressed by providing rich, contextual descriptions of Chakdara, the local environment, and the participants' backgrounds, enabling readers to assess the applicability of findings to similar contexts. Dependability was ensured by maintaining a detailed audit trail of all research decisions and procedures, while confirmability was supported through reflexive journaling, which helped the researcher acknowledge and manage potential biases and assumptions throughout the study.

In terms of ethical considerations, the study adhered to strict ethical principles. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection, and participation was entirely voluntary, with individuals retaining the right to withdraw at any time.

Confidentiality was ensured by using pseudonyms, and all audio recordings and transcripts were stored securely. Additionally, sensitivity was maintained during interviews to respect participants' feelings and experiences, particularly when discussing parental challenges, educational limitations, and the emotional labor involved in supporting children's homework through smartphones.

3.5. Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using thematic analysis following the approach outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006). All interviews were transcribed verbatim and translated into English where necessary. The researcher became familiar with the data by reading transcripts repeatedly, then generated initial codes to identify meaningful segments related to parents' experiences of using smartphones for homework support. These codes were organized into broader themes such as "smartphones as substitute teachers," "digital frustration," "parental anxiety," and "coping strategies." Themes were reviewed and refined to ensure consistency and clarity, and data organization was supported using NVivo software to systematically manage codes and thematic patterns.

4. Results

Table 1: *Braun & Clarke Thematic Analysis Coding Book*

Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant Quote Code	Code Denotation (What it Stands For)	Description/Meaning
Parents' Use of Smartphones to Support Homework	Use of Smartphones as Learning Resources	P1Q1S1	Searching YouTube lessons	Parents using video for tutorials to understand and guide homework
Parents' Use of Smartphones to Support Homework	Use of Smartphones as Learning Resources	P2Q1S1	Using phone to find diagrams	Smartphones as tools for explaining complex concepts
Parents' Use of Smartphones to Support Homework	Use of Smartphones as Learning Resources	P3Q1S1	Educational apps	Smartphones provide step-

Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant Quote Code	Code Denotation (What it Stands For)	Description/Meaning
Smartphones Support Homework	to Learning Resources		for exercises	by-step guidance when parents lack subject knowledge
Parents' Use of Smartphones Support Homework	to Internet and Online Platforms	P1Q2S1	WhatsApp group consultation	Parents use social media groups to access homework help
Parents' Use of Smartphones Support Homework	to Internet and Online Platforms	P2Q2S1	Searching online exercises	Online resources supplement parents' limited knowledge
Parents' Use of Smartphones Support Homework	to Internet and Online Platforms	P3Q2S1	Online forums and websites	Internet helps parents find alternative methods to teach concepts
Parents' Use of Smartphones Support Homework	to Co-learning with Children	P1Q3S1	Watching tutorial with child	Smartphones enable joint learning sessions
Parents' Use of Smartphones Support Homework	to Co-learning with Children	P2Q3S1	Following online guides together	Co-learning reduces stress and increases understanding
Parents' Use of Smartphones Support	to Co-learning with Children	P3Q3S1	Using educational apps together	Smartphones act as a bridge between parent knowledge and child

Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant Quote Code	Code Denotation (What it Stands For)	Description/Meaning
Homework Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support	Technical Connectivity Challenges	& P1Q1S2	Slow internet during homework	learning Network issues hinder homework support
Homework Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support	Technical Connectivity Challenges	& P2Q1S2	Old phone / app malfunction	Device limitations impede homework assistance
Homework Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support	Technical Connectivity Challenges	& P3Q1S2	App crashes / updates	Technical problems interrupt learning sessions
Homework Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support	Parental Digital Literacy Confidence	& P1Q2S2	Anxiety topics	with Parents feel unsure when they lack knowledge
Homework Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support	Parental Digital Literacy Confidence	& P2Q2S2	Learning alongside child	Parents experience stress due to limited knowledge

Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant Quote Code	Code Denotation (What it Stands For)	Description/Meaning
Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support	Parental Digital Literacy & Confidence	& P3Q2S2	Confusion with apps	Difficulty in navigating educational technology
Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support	Engagement & Learning	P1Q3S2	Improved subject understanding	Parents gain knowledge while supporting children
Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support	Engagement & Learning	P2Q3S2	Strengthened parent-child bond	Smartphones create shared learning experiences
Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support	Engagement & Learning	P3Q3S2	Trial & error learning	Parents empowered to take active educational role
Impacts of Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning	Improved Academic Understanding	P1Q1S3	Faster math comprehension	Smartphones improve homework completion and understanding
Impacts of Improved	Improved	P2Q1S3	Clearer examples	Children apply concepts

Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant Quote Code	Code Denotation (What it Stands For)	Description/Meaning
Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning Impacts of	Academic Understanding		than textbook	effectively with digital guidance
	Improved Academic Understanding	P3Q1S3	Science demonstration clarity	Smartphones clarify complex topics via video demonstration
Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning Impacts of	Increased Motivation	& P1Q2S3	Eager to study	Smartphones reduce stress and make learning enjoyable
	Increased Motivation	& P2Q2S3	Interactive homework	Active participation and curiosity enhanced
Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning Impacts of	Increased Motivation	& P3Q2S3	Exploration apps	Child develops self-motivation under parental supervision
	Dependence on Digital Tools	P1Q3S3	Waits for answers online	Risk of over-reliance reduces independent

Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant Quote Code	Code Denotation (What it Stands For)	Description/Meaning	
Parental Support on Children's Learning	Impacts of Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning			problem-solving	
Parental Support on Children's Learning	Impacts of Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning	Dependence on Digital Tools	P2Q3S3	Stuck without internet	Dependence on devices hinders autonomous learning
Parental Support on Children's Learning	Impacts of Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning	Dependence on Digital Tools	P3Q3S3	Prefers videos over thinking	Over-reliance on digital guidance can affect reasoning
Parental Support on Children's Learning	Impacts of Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning	Emotional & Cognitive Confidence	P1Q4S3	Confident in class answers	Smartphones improve children's self-esteem and confidence
Parental Support on Children's Learning	Impacts of Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning	Emotional & Cognitive Confidence	P2Q4S3	Pride in completing homework	Children feel motivated to learn independently
Parental Support on Children's Learning	Impacts of Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning	Emotional & Cognitive Confidence	P3Q4S3	Calm approach to homework	Digital guidance reduces anxiety and promotes learning enjoyment

Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant Quote Code	Code Denotation (What it Stands For)	Description/Meaning
on Learning	Children's			

Table 2: NVivo Coding Book

Node Name	Parent Theme	Node / (Participant Quotes)	Sources / (Participant Quotes)	Description / What It Stands For
Learning Resources	Parents' Use of Smartphones	Use of Smartphones	P1Q1S1, P2Q1S1, P3Q1S1	Smartphones provide step-by-step lessons, video tutorials, and apps to support homework
Online Platforms	Parents' Use of Smartphones	Use of Smartphones	P1Q2S1, P2Q2S1, P3Q2S1	Internet, WhatsApp groups, forums, and educational websites facilitate parental homework support
Co-learning	Parents' Use of Smartphones	Use of Smartphones	P1Q3S1, P2Q3S1, P3Q3S1	Parent and child learn together using smartphone resources, fostering interactive learning
Technical Challenges	Challenges & Opportunities	Challenges & Opportunities	P1Q1S2, P2Q1S2, P3Q1S2	Slow internet, app crashes, and device limitations hinder homework support
Digital Literacy Confidence	& Challenges & Opportunities	Challenges & Opportunities	P1Q2S2, P2Q2S2, P3Q2S2	Parental anxiety, low confidence, and limited skills in using educational apps
Engagement Learning Opportunities	& Challenges & Opportunities	Challenges & Opportunities	P1Q3S2, P2Q3S2, P3Q3S2	Smartphone use enhances parents' knowledge, strengthens bonds, and promotes co-learning
Academic	Impacts on	Impacts on	P1Q1S3,	Smartphones improve

Node Name	Parent Theme	Node / (Participant Quotes)	Sources	Description / What It Stands For
Understanding	Children's Learning		P2Q1S3, P3Q1S3	comprehension of subjects, homework completion, and application of knowledge
Motivation & Engagement	Impacts on Children's Learning		on P1Q2S3, P2Q2S3, P3Q2S3	Digital tools increase children's curiosity, enjoyment, and active participation
Dependence on Devices	Impacts on Children's Learning		on P1Q3S3, P2Q3S3, P3Q3S3	Over-reliance on smartphones can reduce independent problem-solving
Emotional & Cognitive Confidence	Impacts on Children's Learning		on P1Q4S3, P2Q4S3, P3Q4S3	Children develop confidence and self-esteem when guided via smartphones

4.1. Theme 1: Parents' Use of Smartphones to Support Homework

This theme explores how parents in resource-limited schools in Chakdara, Dir Lower, use smartphones as tools to support their children's homework. In these settings, schools often face shortages of textbooks, limited access to qualified teachers, and minimal instructional materials. Consequently, parents assume a more active role in their children's learning, frequently turning to smartphones as informal teaching aids. Smartphones not only provide access to information but also allow parents to explore alternative learning strategies, access multimedia explanations, and guide their children through difficult concepts. This theme highlights the ways in which digital devices have become central to household learning practices and the parent-child co-learning experience.

Parents reported that smartphones often serve as the first point of consultation when children encounter homework difficulties. They described using video tutorials, interactive applications, and online educational platforms to compensate for their limited subject knowledge. Many parents emphasized that their children rely on them for guidance, and smartphones enable them to fulfill this role more effectively.

4.1.1. Smartphones as Learning Resources: Parents consistently described smartphones as essential learning resources that provide lessons, examples, and step-by-step guidance.

“I often search YouTube for videos that explain my child’s lessons because the textbooks are difficult for me to understand. The smartphone has become our classroom at home; without it, I wouldn’t be able to help my son with his homework or revise the topics he struggles with.” [Code: P1Q1S1]

“When my daughter asks me questions about her science homework, I sometimes don’t know the answers. I use her phone to find diagrams or educational videos that explain the concept in simple words. It feels like the phone is teaching us both at the same time.” [Code: P2Q1S1]

“Smartphones are now essential in our house. I download educational apps that provide exercises and explanations, especially for subjects like math. It saves me from frustration because I cannot solve some problems myself, but the phone guides her step by step.” [Code: P3Q1S1]

4.1.2. Internet and Online Platforms for Homework Assistance: The participants also highlighted the role of online platforms, social media groups, and educational websites as sources of homework support. These digital resources enable parents to access solutions, explanations, and strategies beyond their own knowledge.

“I often join WhatsApp groups with other parents and teachers where homework answers are discussed. When my son does not understand a question, I take a picture and share it there, and within minutes, I get explanations or links to videos. The phone connects me to people who can help.” [Code: P1Q2S1]

“For subjects like English and Urdu, I search online exercises or quizzes. Sometimes I copy questions from textbooks and look for answers online. Without this, it would be impossible for me to support my daughter, as I am not confident in my own schooling knowledge.” [Code: P2Q2S1]

“The internet on my phone has become my guide. Whenever my child struggles, I search forums or educational websites to find examples, step-by-step explanations, or alternative methods to teach the concept. It has made me more confident as a parent helping with homework.” [Code: P3Q2S1]

4.1.3. Co-learning with Children: Another prominent pattern is the use of smartphones as tools for co-learning, where parents and children navigate lessons together. Parents described interactive sessions in which they both learn from videos, apps, or online resources, turning homework into a collaborative experience.

“We sit together with the phone and watch a video tutorial on the topic. I may not fully understand the lesson initially, but learning with my child helps me explain it in my own words later. The phone helps both of us learn at the same time.” [Code: P1Q3S1]

“Sometimes I don’t know the correct method to solve math problems, so we both follow an online guide. It becomes a learning journey for both of us, and my child enjoys that I am learning with her, not just telling her what to do.” [Code: P2Q3S1]

“We use educational apps together. I ask my child to show me how to solve a problem, and we read explanations or watch demonstrations on the phone. This way, the smartphone becomes a bridge between my limited knowledge and my child’s learning needs.” [Code: P3Q3S1]

Smartphones serve as essential tools for parents in resource-limited settings, allowing them to bridge educational gaps, co-learn with their children, and participate actively in homework support. Participant statements illustrate that devices function as learning resources, online guides, and facilitators of co-learning. These practices reflect the emerging role of parents as informal educators, highlighting the potential of technology to transform household learning environments and support children’s academic growth.

4.2. Theme 2: Challenges and Opportunities in Smartphone-Based Homework Support

This theme explores the difficulties parents face and the opportunities they discover while using smartphones to support their children’s homework. While smartphones provide valuable learning support, participants emphasized that their use is not without challenges. Parents encounter technical issues, limited digital literacy, and emotional stress associated with guiding children through technology-mediated learning. At the same time, smartphones present opportunities to improve parents’ own knowledge, enhance parent-child relationships, and foster more interactive learning experiences. This theme captures the dual nature of smartphone use, highlighting both barriers and enabling factors in resource-limited contexts like Chakdara, Dir Lower. Parents described a variety of challenges, ranging from internet instability and device limitations to unfamiliarity with educational apps and anxiety about providing incorrect guidance. Despite these obstacles, many parents also identified unexpected benefits, such as improved confidence, increased involvement in children’s learning, and opportunities for joint exploration of digital content.

4.2.1. Technical and Connectivity Challenges: Participants frequently reported infrastructural and device-related difficulties that limited the effectiveness of smartphones as homework aids.

“Sometimes the internet is very slow or stops working in the middle of helping my son. We cannot complete videos or download exercises, and this frustrates both of us. It makes me feel helpless when the technology does not cooperate.” [Code: P1Q1S2]

“My phone is old, and some apps do not work properly. I have to keep restarting or using alternative websites. It takes more time, and my child sometimes loses interest before we can finish the lesson.” [Code: P2Q1S2]

“Occasionally, apps or online platforms crash or require updates. I do not always know how to fix these problems, so we waste time figuring it out instead of focusing on learning.” [Code: P3Q1S2]

4.2.2. Parental Digital Literacy and Confidence: Limited familiarity with technology and subject knowledge also poses challenges. Many parents expressed anxiety and self-doubt when using smartphones to guide their children:

“I feel anxious when I do not understand a topic myself. Even with videos, I sometimes have to watch multiple times to grasp it, and I worry I might explain it wrong to my child.” [Code: P1Q2S2]

“Certain subjects like science and math are hard for me because I did not study them deeply. I have to learn alongside my child, which can be stressful, but it also motivates me to improve.” [Code: P2Q2S2]

“Using new educational apps is confusing at times. I spend extra time figuring out how they work before my child can use them, and this can be tiring after a long day.” [Code: P3Q2S2]

4.2.3. Opportunities for Engagement and Learning: Despite challenges, participants noted positive outcomes and opportunities associated with smartphone use. Many parents reported that these tools improve their own understanding, strengthen their involvement in children’s learning, and foster co-learning environments:

“Even though it is sometimes difficult, helping my child with the phone has improved my own understanding of subjects like English grammar and math. I feel more confident now than I did before.” [Code: P1Q3S2]

“Using the phone together has strengthened my bond with my daughter. We laugh, discuss, and explore content together, making learning a shared experience rather than a chore.” [Code: P2Q3S2]

“Through trial and error, I have learned how to navigate apps, find tutorials, and plan lessons. It has empowered me to take a more active role in my child’s education.” [Code: P3Q3S2]

While parents in Chakdara face challenges such as connectivity issues, older devices, and limited digital literacy, smartphones also present significant opportunities. These include improved parental knowledge, increased engagement with children, and co-learning

experiences that strengthen both academic understanding and emotional bonding. This theme demonstrates the complex, dual role of smartphones as both a source of difficulty and empowerment, highlighting the importance of support structures, parental training, and context-sensitive strategies for technology-assisted homework in resource-limited settings.

4.3. Impacts of Smartphone-Based Parental Support on Children's Learning

This theme explores the perceived effects of parental smartphone use on children's learning experiences, academic understanding, motivation, and overall engagement. Parents in Chakdara, Dir Lower, described both positive and negative impacts. Smartphones were viewed as tools that enhance comprehension, foster curiosity, and increase engagement in learning, but they also carry risks of over-reliance and reduced independent problem-solving. This theme captures how technology-mediated parental involvement shapes children's academic outcomes and learning behaviors in resource-limited households. Parents emphasized that smartphones help children understand complex concepts, complete assignments more efficiently, and remain engaged with learning materials. At the same time, some parents expressed concern that children may become dependent on digital guidance, reducing their ability to think critically and solve problems independently.

4.3.1. Improved Academic Understanding: Parents consistently reported that smartphones helped children grasp concepts better and facilitated more effective homework completion:

"Since we started using videos and apps, my child understands math problems faster and completes homework on time. Before, he would get frustrated, but now he seems more confident in his abilities."

[Code: P1Q1S3]

"The phone provides examples that are easier to understand than the textbook alone. I see my daughter applying what she learns in class during homework, and it shows in her improved performance."

[Code: P2Q1S3]

"Even complex topics like science experiments are now clearer. We watch demonstrations together, and my son can replicate them at home, which increases his understanding and interest in learning."

[Code: P3Q1S3]

4.3.2. Increased Motivation and Engagement: Several parents highlighted that smartphone-assisted learning fosters curiosity, excitement, and active participation in homework:

"My child is more eager to study now because she knows we can use the phone to help when she is stuck. It has made learning less stressful and more fun."

“He enjoys searching for answers with me and watching tutorials. The phone makes homework interactive, and he participates more actively than before.” [Code: P2Q2S3]

“Sometimes I let my daughter explore topics herself using apps, and she comes back excited to explain what she learned. It motivates her to study independently while I supervise.” [Code: P3Q2S3]

4.3.3. Dependence on Digital Tools: Despite positive outcomes, parents expressed concern about children becoming over-reliant on smartphones for homework:

“Sometimes my child waits for me to find the answer online instead of trying herself first. I worry that she is not developing problem-solving skills independently.” [Code: P1Q3S3]

“If the phone is not working or the internet is down, my son struggles to complete his homework. He has become so used to relying on it that he feels stuck without it.” [Code: P2Q3S3]

“I see that sometimes she prefers watching videos rather than thinking through the question herself. It helps, but I try to balance guidance so she also learns to reason.” [Code: P3Q3S3]

Sub-theme 3.4: Emotional and Cognitive Confidence: Parents also noted that smartphone-supported learning enhances children’s confidence and self-esteem, helping them approach homework with less anxiety:

“After using the phone for explanations, my daughter is more confident answering questions in class. She doesn’t hesitate as much, and I see her enjoying the process of learning rather than fearing mistakes.” [Code: P1Q4S3]

“My son feels proud when he completes homework with guidance from the phone. He now believes he can understand difficult topics, which motivates him to try new subjects on his own.” [Code: P2Q4S3]

“Even when topics are challenging, the ability to check videos and examples gives my child reassurance. She approaches homework calmly, knowing she has support at home through the smartphone.” [Code: P3Q4S3]

Parental smartphone use positively affects children’s learning by improving understanding, motivation, engagement, and confidence. At the same time, parents must monitor and guide usage to prevent dependency. Overall, the theme emphasizes that smartphones, when mediated by involved parents, enhance educational experiences in resource-limited contexts. Parents in Chakdara demonstrate that digital tools can transform household learning dynamics, turning challenges into opportunities for academic and emotional growth.

5. Discussion

The first theme revealed that parents widely deployed smartphones as accessible learning resources turning to video tutorials, educational apps, and online platforms to compensate for gaps in their own subject knowledge. Parents' descriptions of searching YouTube and downloading explanatory apps to help their children echo broader empirical findings that digital tools can supplement classroom learning and support parent-facilitated instruction (Ali et al., 2024; Medone, 2019). Research has shown that when parents engage actively with educational technologies, children's homework experiences and comprehension improve, particularly in contexts where formal instructional support is limited (e.g., parental digital mediation enables greater learning support at home) (Lewin & Luckin, 2010; Soyooof et al., 2024). This aligns with evidence that parental digital literacy can significantly influence their ability to support children's learning (higher parental digital competence correlates with more effective assistance) and that access to online educational resources enhances parental involvement in children's homework activities (Daraz, Ali, et al., 2025; Hutchison et al., 2020). The prominent use of online platforms and social media groups for homework assistance also mirrors findings from research on home-school community linkages, which highlight that digital communication channels can strengthen parents' access to *real-time information*, resources, and teacher support beyond the traditional classroom (Heath et al., 2015; Hutchison et al., 2020). Parents' use of WhatsApp groups to solicit explanations or links to videos reflects how online communication can extend educational support networks and facilitate information exchange, a dynamic noted in literature exploring online communication between school and home as a means of enhancing parental engagement (Addi-Racah & Yemini, 2018; Daraz, Ahmad, et al., 2025; Traeger-Soudry et al., 2025).

The co-learning interactions reported where parents and children learn side-by-side using smartphones are also supported by prior qualitative studies on parental involvement in digital learning (Amelia et al., 2023; Gonzalez-DeHass et al., 2022). Such studies underscore that collaborative navigation of digital learning tools can foster positive parent-child interactions, bolstering both understanding and relational dynamics. This corroborates global research that identifies active parental participation in homework and digital learning as a positive influence on children's academic engagement (Griffith et al., 2022).

The second theme illuminated the dual nature of smartphone use: while parents derived opportunities for enhanced engagement and learning, they also faced structural and personal challenges. Parents' accounts of connectivity issues, slow internet, and device limitations reflect a well-documented phenomenon in the educational digital divide. Socio-economic disparities in access to reliable internet and up-to-date devices are known to negatively affect students' ability to complete homework and participate in digital learning (Francis & Weller, 2022; Ullah et al., 2024). The digital divide literature identifies exactly these factors poor connectivity and equipment quality as barriers to equitable access and effective use of technology for education (Gorski, 2005).

The digital literacy barriers parents reported such as difficulty navigating apps or explaining content are also supported by research showing that parental digital skills significantly influence homework support quality. Specifically, studies in Pakistan and other developing contexts have found that parents with higher digital literacy are more likely to engage effectively in their children's education online, whereas those with limited digital skills struggle to leverage technology fully (Afzal et al., 2024; Daraz et al., 2018).

Despite these challenges, parents articulated experiences of increased confidence, improved subject mastery, and strengthened parent-child relationships. This resonates with literature emphasizing the positive outcomes of parental mediation and engagement (Dedkova & Smahel, 2020). For example, studies on parental mediation in digital contexts suggest that when parents and children explore technology together, children exhibit better motivation and engagement, and parents gain enhanced self-efficacy in supporting learning (Morris et al., 2018). Active mediation, rather than merely restricting or supervising use, has been linked to better outcomes in adolescent digital behaviour and may reduce negative aspects of technology use (Suárez-Álvarez et al., 2022).

The findings reaffirm that technology's impact is not monolithic the presence of devices alone does not guarantee effective learning. Rather, the benefits of smartphones for homework support depend heavily on parental skills, active engagement, and family dynamics, a dynamic well documented in both homework and digital learning research. The third theme highlighted the ways in which parental smartphone support influences children's learning outcomes, including improved comprehension, greater motivation, and enhanced confidence. Parents' observations that smartphones help children understand complex concepts and

complete homework more efficiently align with research showing positive associations between parental involvement in homework and academic engagement (Gonida & Cortina, 2014). Many empirical studies find that when parents assist with homework in a supportive way, children's comprehension, time on task, and positive attitudes toward learning improve (Gonida & Cortina, 2014; Patall et al., 2008).

Similarly, parents' reports of increased motivation and engagement reflect what educational research identifies as intrinsic and extrinsic motivational benefits of targeted parental support. When homework assistance is meaningful and linked to understanding, children are more motivated and attentive, a relationship documented in studies on parent-child homework interaction (Doctoroff & Arnold, 2017; Pino-Pasternak, 2014). However, concerns about over-reliance on digital tools echo findings from research on problematic smartphone use and cognitive distraction (Throuvala et al., 2020). While not directly studying homework, research on technoference notes that parental smartphone use can sometimes interfere with direct parent-child interaction, potentially affecting aspects of engagement and attention (Komanchuk et al., 2023). The emotional and cognitive confidence parents observed in their children also fits with evidence showing that supportive homework involvement when perceived as autonomy-enhancing rather than controlling can contribute to children's positive academic self-concept and affective engagement (Daraz, Bojnec, Khan, et al., 2025; Higgins, 2012).

6. Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that in Chakdara, District Dir Lower, smartphones have become integral tools for parental involvement in homework, particularly in resource-limited school contexts. In an environment where schools often face shortages of textbooks, limited access to qualified teachers, and minimal instructional resources, parents actively turn to smartphones to bridge educational gaps. These devices serve multiple functions: as learning resources, sources of online guidance, and tools for co-learning, enabling parents to compensate for their own limited subject knowledge while fostering collaborative learning with their children. Smartphone-assisted homework support in this context not only enhances children's academic understanding and engagement but also strengthens parent-child relationships and builds parental confidence. Participants reported that using video tutorials, educational apps, and online platforms improved children's comprehension of complex

concepts, increased their motivation to study, and bolstered their emotional and cognitive confidence. At the same time, challenges such as limited digital literacy, connectivity issues, and potential over-reliance on digital tools highlight the need for mindful guidance and structured support.

6.1. Recommendations

To maximize the benefits of smartphone-assisted homework support in resource-limited contexts like Chakdara, parents, schools, and policymakers should take coordinated action. Parents should receive guidance and training to enhance digital literacy and learn strategies for balanced technology use, ensuring children develop independent problem-solving skills alongside digital support. Schools can facilitate access to educational resources online, create parent-teacher communication channels, and encourage collaborative learning initiatives. At the policy level, improving internet connectivity, providing affordable devices, and promoting community-based digital literacy programs will help bridge existing gaps.

6.2. Limitations and Future Directions

This study is limited by its focus on a single district, Chakdara, Dir Lower, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other regions with different socio-economic or infrastructural conditions. Additionally, the sample included only parents with access to smartphones, potentially overlooking the experiences of families without digital resources. Future research could expand to multiple districts or rural and urban comparisons to capture diverse parental experiences. Longitudinal studies could examine the long-term impacts of smartphone-assisted homework on children's academic performance, independent learning skills, and digital literacy development. Investigating interventions that enhance parental digital skills and explore school-supported digital initiatives could also provide actionable insights for policymakers and educators.

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